

Ion-Solvent Interaction of Amino Acids. IV. Apparent Molal Volumes of Amino Acids in Neutral, Acidic and Alkaline Media at Different Temperatures

M. M. BHATTACHARYA** and M. SENGUPTA*

Department of Pure Chemistry, University College of Science, University of Calcutta, Calcutta-700 009

The densities of aqueous solutions of several α , β and γ amino acids at three different pH's have been measured at three temperatures between 30 and 40° in the concentration range of 0.005 to 0.1 M, and the apparent molal volumes have been calculated. The ϕ_v values have been properly extrapolated, and the values at infinite dilution obtained. It has been found that $\phi_v^{\circ}(\text{NaOH}) > \phi_v^{\circ}(\text{HCl}) > \phi_v^{\circ}(\text{water})$. Also, all the amino acids in neutral solution show an increase in ϕ_v° value with temperature, whereas in 0.1N NaOH or in 0.1N HCl the ϕ_v° values appear to remain unchanged. The results of this investigation have been compared with those obtained from previous studies of viscosity B-coefficient for the same systems. The interactions of the two charge groups in amino acids with the solvent molecules have been shown to be mutually dependent. The number of water molecules hydrated to each of the three different ionic forms has been calculated.

RECENTLY there has been an increased interest in attempts to understand the role of water solvated to soluble organics in the living cells, because of the fact that most biological macromolecules are physiologically active in aqueous solutions¹. Amino acids constitute in the most part important constituents of such soluble organics; as a result, thermodynamic, kinematic, *etc.* studies using these compounds in aqueous solutions, which may be expected to reflect the structural interactions with water molecules as in the case of simple electrolytes, would be pertinent and interesting.

An amino acid may exist in solution in several possible forms, depending on the pH of the medium^{2,3}. This makes it possible to study the effect of the nature of the ionic charge on the property studied, with the advantage of having the size and structure of the solute molecule remaining almost unaltered. Gurney⁴ has considered that the zwitterionic form of an amino acid may be thought of as a bar magnet, having a similar pattern of lines of force around it. The total energy in this field will not be as large as that associated with the fields of two small separate ions, but somewhat less. It would thus be interesting to study the nature of ion-solvent interactions of the two ionic and the zwitterionic forms of the same amino acid in water, so that a mutual comparison of the extent of the said interaction in the above three cases could be made, in order to put the contention of Gurney to some sort of experimental verification.

In order to acquire an insight into the nature of the above mentioned interaction, experimental investigations by the density and heat capacity

measurement methods have been found to be very fruitful⁵⁻⁸. This is not only due to the simplicity of the said experimental techniques, but also to the fact that the derived standard partial molal values of the quantities measured provide specific information about the nature of the particular types of solute-solvent interactions occurring for the different constituent parts of an organic molecule, say, utilising the simple additive nature of the thermodynamic properties mentioned.

Previous studies of amino acids in water by the density and heat capacity measurement methods carried out by Ahluwalia *et al.*⁵, Millero *et al.*¹ and Shahidi and Farrel⁹ indicate that the experimental $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ values of amino acids differ considerably from (i) those of the corresponding uncharged isomers, (ii) the values calculated on the basis of the different group contributions to $\bar{V}^{\circ}$, or (iii) those obtained by other methods, such as that developed by Terasawa *et al.*¹⁰. This apparent anomaly between the experimentally measured and the predicted values was shown to be due essentially to the ionisation of the amino acids in the solvent.

The volume changes during the first and second step proton ionisation of a large number of α , ω -amino acids were also studied by Lepori and Mollica¹¹ and Shahidi and Farrel⁹, using the partial molal volumes of the amino acids, their hydrochlorides and sodium salts, at one temperature (25°) only. The two groups of workers have made apparently contradictory suggestions as to whether the interactions with the solvent molecules by the two charge centres in such molecules are independent of each other or not.

** Present address: Department of Chemistry, Bangabasi Evening College, Calcutta-700 009.

A study of such interactions of amino acids from the complementary view-points of viscosity B-coefficient as well as partial molal volume measurements may be expected to throw new light on the nature of the problem. Studies of ion-solvent interaction of the different ionic forms of five amino acids from the standpoint of viscosity measurements have been reported elsewhere^{1,2}. It is the purpose of the present paper to report the apparent molal volume measurements of the same five amino acids at different pH's and temperatures. Density measurements have been made for glycine, dl α -alanine, β -alanine and 2-amino- and 4-aminobutyric acids in (i) water, (ii) 0.1 N HCl and (iii) 0.1 N NaOH at 30°, 35° and 40°. The results have been compared with those obtained from viscosity measurements.

Experimental

A saturated solution of medicinal glycine (E. Merck) in warm water was shaken with decolorising carbon, filtered, and precipitated by the addition of methanol; the operation was repeated. The white crystalline product was dried at 110° for 12 h. dl α -Alanine (analytical grade, Reanal) was used without further purification. β -Alanine (E. Merck), dl 2-aminobutyric acid (B D.H.) and 4-aminobutyric acid (Purum, Fluka) were purified similarly as in the case of glycine, precipitations being done with ethanol. All the amino acids were dried at 100° for ~ 2 h before being dissolved in double-distilled water (from an all pyrex still), or 0.1 N HCl, or 0.1 N NaOH, as appropriate, and the solutions were prepared and dilutions made (again, with water, or the above acid or alkali solutions as appropriate) on molal basis. [Only three solutions in HCl (one each for glycine, β -alanine and 4-aminobutyric acid, all at 35°) had slightly larger amino acid concentration than that of the free acid (0.1 N)]. As a result of this method of solution preparation, the concentration of the amino acid hydrochloride, or the sodium salt, changed gradually, but the ionic strength of the medium remained effectively constant. Three to five solutions of each of the amino acids were prepared in the concentration range 0.005 to 0.1 M[†].

The densities of the solutions were measured in a 50 cm³ specific gravity bottle, and are precise to $\pm 10^{-5}$ g cm⁻³ (bouyancy corrections not made). A constant temperature bath, controlled to within $\pm 0.005^\circ$ was used at the three different temperatures. The literature values^{1,2} of the density of water used in the calculations were 0.99568, 0.99406 and 0.99220 g cm⁻³ at 30°, 35° and 40°, respectively.

† The present study is restricted to very dilute solutions, almost to a fraction of the concentration range of earlier studies^{9,11}. As a result, while the intercepts of the linear plots (i.e. ϕ_v^0) agree with the earlier results, the slopes (h and a) are different to varying extents. We are concerned with the ϕ_v^0 values only.

Results

The apparent molal volumes of the different amino acids in neutral aqueous, 0.1 N HCl and 0.1 N NaOH solutions, were calculated with the help of the equation,

$$\phi_v = \frac{1}{m} \left(\frac{1000 + mM_s}{\rho_m} - \frac{1000}{\rho_0} \right) \quad (1)$$

where, m and ρ_m are respectively the molality and density of the solution, M_s the molecular weight of the solute, and ρ_0 the density of the solvent medium. For ϕ_v calculations in alkaline or acidic solutions, the densities of 0.1 N alkali or 0.1 N acid respectively were used for ρ_0 , the effective contribution to ϕ_v would then be due to the respective ionic form of the amino acid. The results are recorded in Table 1.

The apparent molal volumes at infinite dilution of the amino acids in acid or alkaline solutions were obtained from a computerised least-square fit of the Redlich-Meyer equation¹³ in the form,

$$\phi_v - S_v \sqrt{c} = \phi_v^0 + hc \quad (2)$$

where, h is an empirical constant, and S_v the Debye-Hückel limiting slope, the different values of which at the different temperatures were taken from literature¹³. The ϕ_v^0 values together with the standard deviations (of fit only) of all the five amino acids in acid and alkaline solutions are recorded in Table 2.

Now, since both the sodium salt and the hydrochloride of different amino acids, being salts of weak acid and strong base or *vice versa*, may undergo hydrolysis, or dissociation, in aqueous solution, [viz. (i) $H_2O + A^-Na^+ \rightleftharpoons AH^\pm + NaOH$, and (ii) $AH_2^+Cl^- \rightleftharpoons AH^\pm + HCl$], a correction for this in the ϕ_v values of the amino acid salts has been applied both by Shahidi and Farrel⁹ and Lepori and Mollica¹¹. Since the present investigations, in the case of the salts, have mostly been carried out in either acidic or alkaline media, therefore both the above reactions were presumably suppressed to a large extent. Moreover, calculations of the degree of acid dissociation in the case of chlorides, or hydrolysis in the case of sodium salts, using the first and the second dissociation constants of the amino acids under consideration and following the method of Shahidi and Farrel⁹, show that the said correction would amount to no more than 1 cm³ mol⁻¹ for the former, and ~ 4 cm³ mol⁻¹ for the latter, only in the above mentioned three cases of salts in neutral solution. The extrapolated values (ϕ_v^0) are thus essentially unaffected.

In the case of non-electrolytes and amino acids in neutral solution, a linear dependence of ϕ_v on concentration is generally observed¹⁴,

$$\phi_v = \phi_v^0 + a'c \quad (3)$$

Computerised least-square plots of ϕ_v vs concentration were made for the five amino acids in neutral aqueous solution at the three temperatures; the values of the intercepts (ϕ_v^0), together with the standard deviations (of fit only) are also recorded in Table 2.

TABLE 1—APPARENT MOLAL VOLUMES OF THE FIVE AMINO ACIDS AT DIFFERENT CONCENTRATIONS AND AT THREE DIFFERENT pH'S

	Glycine		α -Alanine		β -Alanine		Butyrine		4-Aminobutyric acid	
	m	ϕ_v cm ³	m	ϕ_v cm ³	m	ϕ_v cm ³	m	ϕ_v cm ³	m	ϕ_v cm ³
30°										
Water			0.088 0	60.8	0.056 4	59.2	0.031 7	77.1	0.080 5	72.8
			0.044 4	60.3	0.032 3	58.8	0.022 9	76.7	0.073 1	73.2
			0.024 4	60.1	0.023 1	59.3	0.016 5	77.2	0.042 5	71.9
0.1 N NaOH	0.077 1	67.3	0.074 9	82.5	0.057 7	82.6	0.048 0	97.7	0.056 4	96.8
	0.041 9	66.7	0.057 8	82.1	0.041 1	82.5	0.038 3	97.3	0.032 8	98.6
	0.022 2	64.2	0.037 5	81.8	0.028 7	82.5	0.025 9	97.8	0.019 4	100.9
0.1 N HCl	0.066 0	50.6	0.068 5	67.9	0.080 3	66.2	0.040 9	84.2	0.085 8	82.6
	0.033 7	50.2	0.050 2	68.2	0.056 4	66.3	0.031 4	84.1	0.052 8	82.4
	0.023 3	50.7	0.031 4	69.7	0.024 5	66.3	0.026 5	84.0	0.048 5	82.6
	0.016 6	47.9					0.019 8	84.6	0.014 6	82.0
35°										
Water	0.093 3	44.2	0.147 7	60.8	0.120 8	58.1	0.035 2	76.4	0.047 1	73.1
	0.083 2	44.5	0.096 4	60.8	0.081 5	58.5	0.025 8	76.2	0.038 7	72.8
	0.032 2	42.6	0.088 5	61.2	0.025 0	60.5	0.016 9	76.8	0.030 9	72.6
0.1 N NaOH	0.041 8	67.5	0.102 7	80.9	0.089 8	81.9	0.047 2	97.9	0.080 4	98.3
	0.030 3	67.2	0.077 2	82.6	0.087 3	82.4	0.036 5	98.0	0.062 9	98.8
	0.022 5	67.2	0.046 7	82.4	0.058 0	82.9	0.018 5	98.9	0.034 2	99.8
0.1 N HCl	0.159 8	47.9	0.069 0	68.3	0.117 0	68.8			0.131 6	81.4
	0.102 6	49.2	0.047 2	68.3	0.064 1	66.1			0.068 2	83.0
	0.034 6	50.9	0.032 1	69.0	0.032 5	66.8			0.047 0	83.9
		0.025 7	69.1							
40°										
Water	0.023 7	44.8	0.079 8	61.3	0.058 6	58.5	0.058 9	75.5	0.079 4	72.9
	0.017 9	44.4	0.063 0	61.6	0.049 7	58.8	0.041 1	75.4	0.046 2	73.5
	0.011 0	43.6	0.046 5	61.9	0.030 7	60.3	0.018 1	76.9	0.015 6	72.6
0.1 N NaOH	0.083 5	66.5	0.083 1	82.8	0.088 4	82.3	0.040 9	98.1	0.071 1	97.4
	0.070 3	66.7	0.046 8	82.7	0.065 3	82.4	0.027 6	98.4	0.063 7	97.8
	0.053 8	66.1	0.042 7	83.7	0.050 1	82.3	0.009 3	98.1	0.045 8	97.9
0.1 N HCl	0.068 4	50.9	0.074 2	68.1	0.091 1	66.5	0.033 3	83.6	0.047 7	83.9
	0.041 9	52.3	0.067 8	68.8	0.058 4	66.5	0.022 1	83.6	0.035 8	84.8
	0.034 8	53.1	0.036 4	70.1	0.045 4	66.2	0.013 5	83.7	0.020 7	85.6

TABLE 2—APPARENT MOLAL VOLUMES (cm³) AT INFINITE DILUTION FOR THE FIVE AMINO ACIDS AT THREE DIFFERENT pH'S AND AT THREE TEMPERATURES

	30°			35°			40°		
	Water	0.1 N NaOH	0.1 N HCl	Water	0.1 N NaOH	0.1 N HCl	Water	0.1 N NaOH	0.1 N HCl
Glycine	39.5	63.45	47.61	41.7	66.62	51.28	42.6	65.90	54.85
α -Alanine	59.8	80.06	70.90	61.4	83.57	69.98	62.9	83.51	71.72
β -Alanine	59.2	81.95	66.18	60.9	85.23	67.10	62.0	81.78	65.72
2-Aminobutyric acid	76.3	98.03	84.47	76.9	99.26	—	77.4	97.91	83.67
4-Aminobutyric acid	71.2	102.42	81.81	71.6	100.49	84.93	72.8	98.7	86.77
	± 0.3	± 0.39	± 0.08	± 0.03	± 0.1	± 0.12	± 0.3	± 0.08	± 0.03

The ϕ_v^0 value for α -alanine at 30° (59.8 cm³) is slightly less than that obtained by Gucker and Allen¹⁵ (60.609 cm³), and Cohn and Edsall¹⁴ (61 cm³), both at 25°, whereas the value for β -alanine at the same temperature (59.1 cm³) is in agreement with their value extrapolated for 30°. Our value

of β -alanine would also be in reasonable agreement with those of Devine and Lowe¹⁶, and Daniel and Cohn¹⁷, if their values are extrapolated to 30°. The value obtained for 2-aminobutyric acid at 30° (76.3 cm³) agrees satisfactorily with that of Ellerton *et al.*¹⁸ (75.628 cm³ at 25°) but is slightly less than

TABLE 3— $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ VALUES (cm^3) OF AMINO ACIDS (i) IN NEUTRAL SOLUTION, (ii) THEIR HYDROCHLORIDES AND (iii) THEIR SODIUM SALTS, TOGETHER WITH THE CORRESPONDING IONIC VALUES FOR THE LAST TWO SPECIES^a, AND THE CORRESPONDING VISCOSITY B-COEFFICIENT VALUES ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$) at 25°

Amino acids	Neutral aqueous solution AH [±]	AH ₂ Cl	AH ₂ [±]	A ⁻ Na ⁺	A ⁻	Viscosity B-coefficient value for neutral amino acids at 25°
Glycine	43.30	68.58	50.75 (43) ^b	43.79	45.00 (61)	0.143
α-Alanine	60.50	86.82	68.99 (71)	59.81	61.02 (77)	—
β-Alanine	58.38	83.90	66.07 (66)	59.67	60.88 (80)	0.220
4-Aminobutyric acid	73.23	100.65	82.82 (78)	75.51	76.72 (103)	0.314

^a From Ref. 11. ^b Figures in parenthesis are values from the present study, extrapolated to 25° from experimental data at 30°, 35° and 45°.

TABLE 4— $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ VALUES (cm^3) FOR (i) ALKYLAMINE HYDROCHLORIDE^a AND (ii) SODIUM SALTS OF ALKYL CARBOXYLIC ACIDS^a TOGETHER WITH THE CORRESPONDING IONIC VALUES FOR THE LAST TWO SPECIES, AND THE CORRESPONDING VISCOSITY B-COEFFICIENT (IONIC) VALUES^b ($\text{dm}^3 \text{mol}^{-1}$)

Electrolytes	$\bar{V}^{\circ}$ at 25°	$\bar{V}^{\circ}_{\text{cation}}$ at 25°	Electrolytes	$\bar{V}^{\circ}$ at 25°	$\bar{V}^{\circ}_{\text{anion}}$ at 25°	$\bar{V}^{\circ}_{\text{cation-}}$ / $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{\text{anion}}$	B _{ion} for R ₁ NH ₃ ⁺ at 25°	B _{ion} for RCOO ⁻ at 25°
CH ₃ NH ₂ Cl	53.93	36.10	CH ₃ COONa	39.31	40.52	4.4	0.047	0.257
C ₂ H ₅ NH ₂ Cl	71.23	53.40	C ₂ H ₅ COONa	53.71	54.92	1.5	0.192	0.399
C ₃ H ₇ NH ₂ Cl	87.33	69.50	C ₃ H ₇ COONa	69.32	70.51	1.0	0.221	0.419
C ₄ H ₉ NH ₂ Cl	103.86	85.53	C ₄ H ₉ COONa	85.69	86.90	1.4	0.368	0.594

^a Ref. 21. ^b Ref. 22.

that reported by Cohn *et al.*¹⁹ (77 cm³ at 25°). The ϕ° values of 4-aminobutyric acid reported by Devine and Lowe¹⁶ at 25° (73.1 cm³) is also greater than that reported here for 30° (71.2 cm³).

Discussion

According to Weber²⁰ the volume of a dipolar ion changes during ionisation: thus the volume of a monoamino-monocarboxylic acid in aqueous solution on being treated with an equivalent amount of HCl or NaOH gets increased by 7.9 cm³ mol⁻¹ of H⁺, or 24 cm³ mol⁻¹ of OH⁻, respectively. In the present study, the average volume increase in acidic solution has been found to be ~ 8-11 cm³, and in alkaline solution ~ 20-30 cm³, over the temperature range 30-40°.

$\bar{V}^{\circ}$ values of amino acids, alkyl amines, and alkyl carboxylate ions: The $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ values for the amino acid hydrochlorides or sodium salts at 25° as reported by Lepori and Mollica¹¹, and Shahidi and Farrel⁹, have been further reduced to the corresponding ionic values by subtracting from these the ionic $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ values of the Cl⁻ and Na⁺ ions²¹, respectively, in order to be able to compare the $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ values of the different ionic forms with the corresponding values of the zwitterionic forms. The values, thus obtained, are shown in Table 3. Further, in order to gain an insight into the nature and extent of the interaction, especially by the two charge centres in the zwitterions, we have also

compiled the $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ values at 25° of n-alkyl amine hydrochlorides and Na-alkyl carboxylates in aqueous solution²². The corresponding ionic $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ values have also been calculated as mentioned above, and shown in Table 4.

Also included in Table 3 are the $\bar{V}^{\circ}_{\text{ionic}}$ values for the amino acids from the present study, extrapolated to 25°. A comparison shows that while our $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ values of the amino acid cations are close to those obtained by Lepori and Mollica¹¹ those for the anions are larger. The difference may be attributed to (apart from the rather uncertain extrapolation) the change in environment under the two slightly different experimental conditions. Whereas Lepori and Mollica have studied the salts in neutral aqueous solution, the present investigations have been carried out mostly in acidic or alkaline medium. Moreover, the anionic $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ values are found to be larger than those of the cationic form in our case, but the reverse was observed by the above workers.

It is interesting to note that the ionic $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ values of the corresponding members (pairs) of the R₁NH₃⁺ and R₁COO⁻ series (i=1 to 4) are quite comparable to each other, so that the difference quantity ($\bar{V}^{\circ}_{\text{R}_1\text{NH}_3^+} - \bar{V}^{\circ}_{\text{R}_1\text{COO}^-}$) in which the alkyl group contribution gets cancelled, is quite small, and nearly constant along the series (1 to 1.5 cm³ mol⁻¹) except for the first member (4.4 cm³ mol⁻¹). One can therefore infer that for these charged groups (NH₃⁺ and COO⁻) the $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ values are

nearly identical, or in other words, that these charged groups interact very similarly with the solvent water.

Now let us consider what happens to this interaction when the two charge centres are joined together in a single molecule, intercepted by an alkyl group, as in amino acids. It is seen from Tables 3 and 4 that experimental $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ values of neutral amino acids (Table 3, 2nd column) are almost half the total ionic $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ values of the corresponding alkyl amine and alkyl carboxylate ions taken together. [In the latter sum, the alkyl group contribution is reckoned twice, however, a correction for this (e.g. methyl group contribution, $\sim 17.3 \text{ cm}^3$) does not essentially alter the conclusion]. Thus, the considerable reduction of the volume of amino acids from the total volume as mentioned indicates that the two charge centres are not independently hydrated as suggested by Shahidi and Farrel⁹, but exert instead considerable influence on each other. Millero *et al.* pointed out that the inductive effect between the two charge groups in amino acids becomes operative, thus resulting in a net reduction in the volume of the zwitterion.

Viscosity B-coefficients of the same systems : For the sake of a better understanding of the nature and extent of interaction of these ions in aqueous solutions, the viscosity B-coefficient data for the same systems as above (amino acid ions¹⁰, RNH_3^{+} , RCOO^{-} ¹⁰) have been compiled, and the corresponding ionic values at 25° are included in Tables 3 and 4. The zwitterionic values at 25° were taken from those reported by Devine and Lowe¹⁰. Here also the same interesting feature is observed, i.e. almost half the sum of the ionic B-values of an alkyl carboxylate anion and the corresponding alkyl amine cation corresponds to the individual B-coefficient value of corresponding zwitterion. (Actually, the calculated values are slightly greater).

Thus, the above finding from the standpoint of viscosity measurement results further substantiates the conclusion that the nature of interaction with the solvent molecules by the two charge centres in an amino acid molecule is considerably different from that in either of the two singly charged species.

Now, it is well known that the greater the electrostriction in a charged molecule the smaller will be its $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ value, whereas the reverse is true in the case of viscosity B-coefficient. As found earlier¹², the ionic B-coefficients of amino acids in water, 0.1 N NaOH and 0.1 N HCl are in the sequence: $B_{\text{water}} > B_{\text{NaOH}} > B_{\text{HCl}}$. To be strictly compatible with this finding, the order of $\bar{V}^{\circ}$ values should have been $\bar{V}_{\text{HCl}}^{\circ} > \bar{V}_{\text{NaOH}}^{\circ} > \bar{V}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\circ}$. But the present investigation of amino acids in presence of free acid or alkali shows that the order is $\bar{V}_{\text{NaOH}}^{\circ} > \bar{V}_{\text{HCl}}^{\circ} > \bar{V}_{\text{H}_2\text{O}}^{\circ}$. On the other hand, the predicted order has been obtained by Lepori and Mollica¹¹, as also Shahidi and Farrel⁹, in neutral aqueous solution

of the chlorides or sodium salts of amino acids. The slight difference in order may be due to experimental error.

Number of water molecules hydrated to the different ionic forms :- It is also interesting to look into the case of hydrated water molecules in the cospheres of the three substantially similar molecules carrying different charges. The number of water molecules hydrated to the zwitterionic, the cationic and the anionic forms of amino acid have been calculated by the method developed by Millero *et al.*¹ according to the following scheme,

$$\bar{V}^{\circ} (\text{charged molecule}) = \bar{V}^{\circ} (\text{int}) + \bar{V}^{\circ} (\text{elect})$$

where, $\bar{V}^{\circ} (\text{int})$ and $\bar{V}^{\circ} (\text{elect})$ are the intrinsic partial molal volume and the electrostrictional partial molal volume, respectively of the appropriate ionic form of the molecule.

The $\bar{V}_{\text{int}}^{\circ}$ values have been estimated by using the crystal molal volumes of amino acids ($\bar{V}_{\text{cryst}}^{\circ} = \frac{\text{Mol. wt.}}{\rho_{\text{cryst}}}$ and $\bar{V}_{\text{int}}^{\circ} = \frac{0.7}{0.6} \bar{V}_{\text{cryst}}^{\circ}$)¹. The crystal density values for the amino acids were taken from literature¹⁴. The thus calculated $\bar{V}_{\text{elect}}^{\circ}$ is related to the number of water molecules (n_{H}) by the following relation¹,

$$n_{\text{H}} = \frac{\bar{V}_{\text{elect}}^{\circ}}{(\bar{V}_{\text{E}}^{\circ} - \bar{V}_{\text{B}}^{\circ})}$$

where, $\bar{V}_{\text{E}}^{\circ}$ and $\bar{V}_{\text{B}}^{\circ}$ are respectively the molar volumes¹ of electrostricted water and bulk water at the same temperature. For electrolyte solutions, the quantity $(\bar{V}_{\text{E}}^{\circ} - \bar{V}_{\text{B}}^{\circ})$ is approximately equal to $-3 \text{ cm}^3 \text{ mol}^{-1}$. The calculated values of n_{H} for the three different ionic forms of amino acids at 25° are shown in Table 5†, along with the corresponding values calculated by using the data of Lepori and Mollica¹¹. (Also included are the data of Millero *et al.*¹ for the zwitterionic forms of two amino acids).

The number of water molecules associated with the three different ionic forms of the same amino acid are seen to be different, the maximum being for the zwitterionic form. This is apparently due to the stronger electrostatic force in such types of molecules. Again, the other two forms, namely, the cationic and the anionic forms are seen to be differently solvated from one another. While the cationic form is seen to retain nearly 3-5 water molecules in the primary solvation sheath, the anionic form¹¹ is seen to be almost unhydrated or only slightly hydrated. On the other hand, viscosity studies indicate an almost reverse trend. Such a reversal of trend was also observed by Sakurai *et al.*¹⁵ for the two different measurements mentioned, viz. the apparent molal volume and viscosity

† The n_{H} values for the amino acid anions are found to be negative, and hence not included in Table 5. This is due to the rather high estimates of $\bar{V}_{\text{anion}}^{\circ}$ obtained.

TABLE 5—VALUES OF μ_H FOR AMINO ACIDS IN THREE DIFFERENT IONIC FORMS

Ions	Glycine			α -Alanine			β -Alanine			2-Aminobutyric acid		
	Zwitter-ion	Cation	Anion	Zwitter-ion	Cation	Anion	Zwitter-ion	Cation	Anion	Zwitter-ion	Cation	Anion
Present	4.09	1.29		3.42	-0.61		3.62	1.29		5.99	2.67	
Ref. 11	2.82	2.25	0.84	2.85	2.68	0.03	3.89	3.06	1.33	6.42	5.25	3.22
Ref. 1	2.63			3.41								

B-coefficient of systems containing alkyl amine cation or carboxylate anion group.

Temperature variation of ϕ_v^0 values: All the amino acids in water show an increase in ϕ_v^0 value, over the temperature range 30-40°. The same has also been observed by other workers²⁵. Ram Gopal *et al.*²⁶ have studied the apparent molal volumes of different amino acids over the extended temperature range 25-70°, and concluded that an appreciable curvature in the ϕ_v^0 vs temperature plots points to strong electrostatic solute-solvent interaction and solvation of the amino acids, similarly as observed in the case of common electrolytes.

The effect of temperature on the ϕ_v^0 values of amino acids, either in 0.1 N NaOH or in 0.1 N HCl solution is not very pronounced, and in most of the case these values appear to remain unchanged over the above temperature range.

Acknowledgement

Financial assistance in the form of Teacher-fellowship, during the tenure of which this work was substantially completed, offered to one of the authors (M.M.B.) by U.G.C., New Delhi, is gratefully acknowledged.

References

1. F. J. MILLERO, A. L. SURDO and C. SHIN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1978, **82**, 784.
2. R. A. COOPER, R. L. LICHTER and J. D. ROBERTS, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1973, **95**, 3724.
3. J. WEBB, R. W. STRICKLAND and F. S. RICHARDSON, *Tetrahedron*, 1978, **29**, 2499.
4. R. W. GURNEY, "Ionic Processes in Solution", McGraw-Hill, New York, 1953.
5. J. C. AHLUWALIA, C. OSTIGUY, G. PERRON and J. E. DESNOYERS, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1977, **55**, 3364.
6. C. JOLICOEUR and G. LACROIX, *Can. J. Chem.*, 1976, **54**, 624.
7. H. HOILAND and E. VIKINGSTUD, *Acta Chem. Scand., Ser. A*, 1976, **30**, 182.
8. S. CABANI, G. CONTI and L. LEPORI, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1974, **78**, 1030.
9. F. SHAHIDI and P. G. FARREL, *J. Chem. Soc., Faraday Trans. 1*, 1981, 963; 1980, 101.
10. S. TERASAWA, H. ITSUKI and S. ARAKAWA, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1975, **79**, 2345.
11. L. LEPORI and V. MOLLIKA, *Z. Phys. Chem.*, 1980, **123**, 51.
12. M. M. BHATTACHARYA and M. SENGUPTA, *Z. Phys. Chem. (N. F.)*, 1980, **121**, 135; 1982, **133**, 79.
13. O. REDLICH and D. M. MEYER, *Chem. Rev.*, 1964, **64**, 221.
14. E. J. COHN and J. T. EDSALL, "Proteins, Amino Acids and Peptides", Reinhold, New York, 1943.
15. F. T. GUCKER and T. W. ALLEN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1942, **64**, 191.
16. W. DEVINE and B. M. LOWE, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1971, 2119.
17. J. DANIEL and E. J. COHN, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1936, **58**, 415.
18. H. D. ELLERTON, G. REINVELDS, D. E. MULCAHY and P. J. DUNCAN, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1964, **68**, 398.
19. E. J. COHN, T. L. McMERKIN, J. T. EDSALL and M. H. BLANCHARD, *J. Am. Chem. Soc.*, 1934, **56**, 784.
20. H. H. WEBER, *Z. Biochem.*, 1930, **1**, 218.
21. P. MUKHERJEE, *J. Phys. Chem.*, 1961, **66**, 740.
22. M. SAKURAI, T. KOMATSU and T. NAKAGAWA, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1975, **48**, 3491.
23. K. TAMAKI, Y. OHAWA, H. KURACHI, M. AKIYAMA and H. ODAKI, *Bull. Chem. Soc. Jpn.*, 1974, **47**, 384.
24. "CRC Hand Book of Physics and Chemistry", Chemical Rubber Co., Cleveland.
25. J. V. TYRELL and M. KENNERLY, *J. Chem. Soc. (A)*, 1968, 2724.
26. RAM GOPAL, D. K. AGARWAL and R. KUMAR, *Indian J. Chem.*, 1973, **11**, 1061.